

Service Learning as an Instrument for Linking Educational Theory with its Practical Application

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Introductory Question

What is your experience with project work in general? Do you integrate project work into your courses?

Next Question

What actually is a project?

Project??? – Research??? –

Free Creativity??? – Regular Task???

Next Question

What actually is a project?

Next Question

What actually is a project? What are its characteristics? A project is ...

- unique and temporary,
- fairly innovative,
- collaborative (shared workload),
- outcome-oriented focusing on “products”,
- “risky” as it has no “correct” results known before,
- of considerable complexity,
- limited in its resources.

Service Learning

What is Service Learning in comparison to a project for educational purposes only?

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6avu1dcKINs>

Service Learning

Service Learning (SL)

- an innovative teaching- and learning-form, which is based on the active use of theoretical knowledge by the students

Goals to be achieved through SL:

- the practical application of the acquired knowledge
- learning skills to enable independent action and self-responsible problem solving
- **development of democratic and responsible civic attitudes and behaviours (the original form: community service)**
- **the ability to act professionally in a specific workplace or another institutional frame (new focus: quid pro quo)**

Methodological approach (original form)

- The students have to work on problems of the community or civil society. They establish links between subject content and their social commitment experiences.
- The learning process is created by linking subject-specific content from university and community involvement of the students.

Service Learning

Methodological approach (new SL focus)

- The learning process is created by linking subject-specific content from university and community involvement of the students.
- In the sense of the economic principle of “quid pro quo” the students fulfil real tasks from working life. This means: companies, firms and other organisations communicate concrete needs to the university course which should be addressed by the students, they place “orders”. The desired services are performed and “delivered” by the students – with the support of the professor and accompanied by the commissioning institution.

Examples of good practice

- Students of architecture and landscaping plan and create an urban garden in a community shelter for refugees.
- Students of civil and environmental engineering support the “Museum für Small Railways” in Naumburg with the partial surveying of a small railway line.
- Students of the Institute of Nutritional Psychology develop a concept for a balanced and age-appropriate diet for a retirement home – taking into account age-related infirmities.

Service Learning (SL)

	New SL focus (Quid Pro Quo)	Original SL form: (Community Service)
Primary intended Beneficiary	Recipient and provider	Recipient
Beneficiary Focus	Service and learning	Service
Intended educational Purposes	Academic development and career development	Civic development, ethic development
Integration with Curriculum	Integrated	Peripheral
Nature of Service Activity	Based on an academic discipline and on an professional needs	Based on a social needs

Service
Learning

vs.

Simulation
Games
and
Case Studies

All forms try to be as authentic as possible and imitate real life, but where do they differ from Service Learning?

Real World Beneficiaries

Players

Professional
Partner 1
(Service
Beneficiary)

Professional
Partner 3
(Service
Beneficiary)

Academic
Sphere:
Professor &
Students
(Service
Providers)

Professional
Partner 2
(Service
Beneficiary)

Professional
Partner 4
(Service
Beneficiary)

The Process of SL

Features and Advantages of SL

- SL responds to a real need, to problems or challenges that actually exist. The students thus do not take on a fake task but a really meaningful one. They are involved in the planning, preparation and implementation of their projects to a significant degree.
- SL projects are not an additional activity outside the current course but are specifically linked to the academic content.
- SL projects take the students out into the “real world” to new places of learning (“flipped classroom”). There they get the opportunity and acquire the skills to master profession-related situations.
- Within the academic framework, students may reflect on their experiences of action and learning.
- The results of the projects are presented, evaluated in detail and acknowledged by the professor and the external partners with an appreciative conclusion (e.g. a certificate, credits etc.).
- There is direct contact between those people who carry out the project and those who benefit from the project.

Regular Classes (no SL)

Was geplant werden muss	
	Zeit (Ablauf, Gewichtung)
	Abwechslung (Rhythmus, Sandwich)
	Kooperation (Sozialformen)
	Transfer in die Praxis
	Wie viel planen?
	Planungsstrategien
	Und ausserdem:
	<small>Spezifische, angestrebte Kompetenzen: Kapitel 5</small>
	<small>Inhalt (Menge, Priorität, Logik, didaktische Reduktion): Kapitel 6</small>
	<small>Abwechslung (Methoden): Kapitel 7, 8 und 9</small>
	<small>Auswertung und Lernkontrolle: Kapitel 13</small>
	<small>Individuelle Lernförderung (Lernstil): Kapitel 10</small>
	<small>Interaktion (Gruppendynamik, Interventionen): Kapitel 11 und 12</small>

BEFORE COURSE

- Teaching Plan
- Organisation of the Lectures

DURING COURSE

- Conducting Lectures

AFTER COURSE

- Grading

Which steps are to be added in the context of SL?

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<i>Zeit (Ablauf, Gewichtung)</i>	
<i>Abwechslung (Rhythmus, Sandwich)</i>	
<i>Kooperation (Sozialformen)</i>	
<i>Transfer in die Praxis</i>	
<i>Wie viel planen?</i>	
<i>Planungsstrategien</i>	
Und ausserdem:	
<small>Lernziele, angestrebte Kompetenzen: Kapitel 5</small>	
<small>Inhalt (Menge, Priorität, Logik, didaktische Reduktion): Kapitel 6</small>	
<small>Abwechslung (Methoden): Kapitel 7, 8 und 9</small>	
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AFTER COURSE

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-

Multiple Roles of the Professor

- In SL, contrary to regular teaching, the teacher's role varies in different learning sequences.
- Which roles?

Application

- Which SL projects can you imagine for your classes?
- Who might be possible “customers”?
- What would be their benefit?
- How could such a SL project be planned step for step?